

Letter to Editor on “Immediate effect of dynamic stretching with and without floss band on hamstring flexibility in futsal players: A pilot study”

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Dear Editor,

We read with great interest the article by Shiza F. Zaidi et al., titled “Immediate effect of dynamic stretching with and without floss band on hamstring flexibility in futsal players: A pilot study,” published in your esteemed journal. We commend the authors for investigating the immediate effects of dynamic stretching with and without a floss band on hamstring flexibility in futsal players. The findings, which demonstrate greater improvements in hamstring flexibility when dynamic stretching is combined with flossing, are noteworthy. However, we would like to highlight a few points requiring further clarification.

Firstly, the keywords provided in the abstract do not adhere to the Medical Subject Headings (MeSH) as specified in the journal’s guidelines.

Secondly, the introduction exceeds the journal’s word limit and does not clearly state a hypothesis. A potential hypothesis could have been: “Dynamic stretching with a floss band improves hamstring flexibility in futsal players,” based on a one-tailed hypothesis. Additionally, the claim that no prior studies have explored the effectiveness of the floss band technique combined with dynamic stretching on hamstring flexibility is not entirely accurate. Similar studies, such as those by Hiroaki Kaneda et al., have investigated this topic.

Thirdly, the Materials and Methods section lacks clarity regarding sample size estimation. There is no mention of the effect size, relevant citations, or the power of the study, which are essential for robust research.

Fourthly, since the flossing technique involves compression and venous constriction, the eligibility criteria are incomplete. Exclusion of participants with hypertension, venous thrombotic disease, heart conditions, or

neuromuscular issues in the lower limbs should have been specified. Moreover, individuals undergoing flexibility training should also have been excluded, as indicated by prior research.

Lastly, the authors could have elaborated on the site of application, technique, and degree of stretch or tension applied when using the floss band. A detailed description would have provided readers with a clearer understanding of the procedure.

In conclusion, while the authors' work is commendable, addressing these concerns would enhance the study's precision and clarity. We hope our suggestions contribute positively to future research in this field.^[1-3]

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